

WP9

Technology and Science Watch

ISBE WP9 REPORT

D 9.8

**Report on the future needs with respect to storage
and hardware**

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II. INTRODUCTION

During the preparatory phase the infrastructure needs to get an estimate of the state of the art with respect to existing and emerging technologies to formulate a technology vision for the construction phase of the infrastructure before starting its actual operation. One of the objectives of WP9 in collaboration with WP2 and WP4 is **Identification of the future needs of the systems biology community with respect to storage and hardware.**

This updated report of the ISBE preparatory phase future needs with respect to storage and hardware might serve as a guide for building up the infrastructure and answer several key questions: what we should watch in the storage and hardware area, what is important for the systems biology community, and how we can use it for ISBE infrastructure.

This report does not aim to provide fully representative data covering all fields in the storage and hardware area, but rather identify demands coming from the community towards the infrastructure and identify the existing state-of-the-art with respect to storage and hardware and show possible future directions and predictions in the usage of storage and hardware in the systems biology community. Systems biology research needs collection and processing of often high throughput data from large numbers of biological experiments using automated procedures and requires the ability to obtain, integrate, analyse and share complex data sets from multiple experimental sources using interdisciplinary tools. The hardware and data storage play the key role in this process.

OBJECTIVES

- **Examination and evaluation of the existing state-of-the-art in storage and hardware in Life sciences**
- **Identifying the demands** of the systems biology community on ISBE hardware and storage

III. THE REPORT

This updated report represents the essence from technology literature watch, gathering information from the systems biology community and data storage and management facilities, a series of surveys and reports, data gained from BIO –IT World Survey and ISBE Wide survey, and by assembling statistical data of systems biology conference proceedings and abstracts. In addition, information is drawn from the report of a recent EU workshop organised by DG CONNECT and DG research and Innovation – ‘HPC in Health Research’ which took place 1-2 October 2014, also a BioMedBridges knowledge exchange workshop hosted by ELIXIR, 15-16 May 2014 “E-Infrastructure support for the life sciences– Preparing for the data deluge” in both of which ISBE participated.

A. 2014 LIFE SCIENCES IT SURVEY

It is essential to diagnose key trends in the life sciences IT space to be able to determine software and hardware usage in the future by systems biology community. In the survey which was conducted by Bio-IT World / Cambridge Healthtech Media Group In January 2014, focusing on the IT Professional within the biotechnology and pharmaceutical industry. The purpose of the study was to explore their budgets, products/vendors used, 2014 initiatives and challenges. With 152 respondents, we can find these trends thanks to responses from senior executives, key opinion leaders in the industry, in life sciences IT –

CIOs and VPs. (43% of respondents were senior IT Directors or IT Managers)

Just under half the respondents work in biotech or pharma, the remainder work in government,

hospital, academia, or vendor organizations.

The survey reports a robust trend for IT investment: 46% expect their IT budgets to increase this year, whereas only 10% anticipate a decrease. 41% of respondents are anticipating increases of 6-10%, while 30% expect even higher increases in spending.

IT Budgets & Purchasing Trends

1. CLOUD COMPUTING- UPDATED

Cloud computing was the most highly cited area for IT spending in 2014, being highlighted by a small majority of respondents. Other key areas include security, workflow technologies, and mobile technologies.

Mobile Technologies, Security and Social media will be a priority area for 2014.

Specific challenges include data storage, security, and staffing levels. Although the respondents stated that cloud computing is highly cited area for IT spending however the survey indicates budget constrains by 39% of respondents as a biggest challenge.

Cloud Solutions & Platforms

- On-premise/Private Cloud Solution ... 18%
- Public Cloud Solution ... 14%
- Hybrid Solutions ... 20%
- Not currently using any cloud based solutions ... 12%
- Currently evaluating solutions ... 10%
- Unsure ... 23%
- Other ... 3%

If using an on-premise/private cloud solution, which are you currently using?*

- Microsoft ... 38%
- VMWare ... 38%
- RedHat... 5%
- HP Cloudmatix ... 10%
- Softlayer ... 5%
- SAP... 5%
- Not using an on-premise/private cloud solution ... 14%
- Other ... 10%

*Respondents were able to choose multiple responses

Roughly between (14-20%) reported using public clouds vs private clouds vs a hybrid cloud platform strategy.

Cloud Solutions & Platforms

Which of the following do you see as the biggest benefit of migrating to the cloud?*

* Respondents were able to choose multiple responses

While some 76% (this is a large increase - only 30% before 2012) respondents reported using Amazon Web Services for their public cloud platform, the report also details a long list of other vendor suppliers for cloud storage platforms.

Cloud Solutions & Platforms

Which applications have you already migrated to the cloud?*

* Respondents were able to choose multiple responses

The most popular cloud application is email (36%), but others scoring highly include Intranet and CRM. From the last report only 18% respondents believe that all their IT platforms will be cloud-based within five years. 51% believe that all their platforms will not migrate to a cloud.

2. DATA STORAGE-UPDATED

In terms of data storage, more than one quarter of respondents are already in the Petabyte storage range, with 20% storing more than 10 PB data (13% increase from the last report). Over 80% respondents expected their data repositories to grow in 2014-2015.

2014 Annual Life Sciences IT Survey

Conducted by:
Bio-IT World

Storage Capacity & Vendors

B. ISBE WIDE SURVEY

ISBE WIDE SURVEY

In order to ensure that ISBE meets the requirements of future systems biologists we are in the process of seeking opinion from key stakeholders in systems biology and related fields. By January 16, 2014 around 100 respondents have completed the online questionnaire (<http://project.isbe.eu/>) and let us know their views on the development of ISBE. In

this report we concentrate on the answers related to future needs with respect to storage and hardware.

1. UNPUBLISHED DATA STORAGE - UPDATED

More than 76% of respondents store their **unpublished data** local to their group, 45% local to institution, 20% cloud-based storage, 24% in a project or programme-wide repository, more than 13% in a community resource. The main reason why most respondents store their unpublished

data local to their group seem to be the fact it is simply for respondents the most comfortable way of storage, in-house, safe and cheap.

We can identify **cloud-based storage** as a potential storage tool in the future. However, it will be necessary to analyse this in detail with respect to ISBE storage and hardware future needs.

Respondents also commented that the objectives for storing the data is mainly to deposit in a 'safe' (i.e. persistent, backed-up) place For some respondents, this could be achieved by access to dropbox or similar, a local computer or institutional server, or even through national or ISBE-wide e-infrastructure.

Q16 Where do you store your unpublished data (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 88 Skipped: 39

2. EXPERIENCED DIFFICULTIES IN MANAGING DATA- UPDATED

Q17 What difficulties have you experienced in managing your data (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 81 Skipped: 46

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014-2015

More than 48% of respondents have experienced **difficulties in managing their data** with respect to storage space. More than 45% have experienced problems with transfer of data. More than 59% have difficulties with long-term storage and 41% with linking data and models and Retrieval of data (27%).

Thus we can identify specific areas that are either not available or sufficiently supported in home institutions, or which cause difficulties for respondents. These should be monitored in the near future and may require targeting for support within the developing ISBE infrastructure. They include: **Long-term storage** (59%), **Back up of data** (almost 52%) with **Standards and curation** (almost 52%).

Additionally some of the respondents replied that the lack of experts to handle large amounts of data, funding for local data management staff; time and funding for community organization are all of concern as well.

Q19 Which public repositories do you submit your data to when your work is published (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 81 Skipped: 46

PRIDE (more than 11%), European Nucleotide Archive (ENA -more than 10%), PDB (more than 10%, PDB Europe 2.6%), PeptideAtlas (9%) and Metabolights (more than 6%) **About 19% do not submit any data to public repositories**, which can be identified as a potential area of ISBE interest. There are several other repositories which are used by a few respondents: IntAct and SABIO-RK (2%), Electron Microscopy Data Bank – EMDB (1%) and BioDare (1%). Other repositories mentioned include dbGAP, SGD, Sage Bio Networks, SYSMO DATABASE, OMERO, non-specified parts of NCBI and EBI sites and ‘supplementary materials’.

3. PUBLIC REPOSITORIES USED FOR PUBLISHED DATA STORAGE - UPDATED

With respect to **respondents submitting data to public repositories at publication**, –it seems that **GEO (almost 36%) and Array Express (more than 28%)** are the repositories which are mostly used. Other repositories reported for published data include

4. PUBLIC REPOSITORIES USED FOR MODELS STORAGE- UPDATED

With respect to submission of models to **public repositories** it seems that **BioModels Database (almost 30%)** is the public repository most used by respondents. About 8% of respondents use JWS Online Repository and more than 5% use CellML public repositories to submit their models. More than 17% do not produce any models. However, many respondents reported that their models are submitted to local (and perhaps non-persistent) repositories - their own or departmental web sites, sometimes externally to project-specific sites, or to their own site and externally to sites such as PlaSMo – (www.plasmo.ed.ac.uk), GINsim model repository, or to non-model-specific repositories such as a SYSMO DATABASE, or Bioconductor/ CRAN.

Q20 Which public repositories do you submit your models to when your work is published (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 78 Skipped: 49

What we can identify as of potential interest to ISBE infrastructure and for further analysis is the fact that more than 48% of respondents do not use any public repositories to submit their models. The reasons for this need to be understood and might suggest that ISBE should attempt to facilitate this in the future.

5. FORMATS USED FOR STRUCTURING AND ANNOTATING DATA- UPDATED

A wide variety of formats were reported for data annotation and mark-up, reflecting the wide range of different data types and modalities required during the systems biology process.

SBML - Systems Biology Mark-up Language is a format used by more than 57% respondents for structuring and annotating their data and models. Respondents also use SAM/BAM - Sequence Alignment Map Format for NGS data (17%), SBGN - Systems Biology Graphical Notation (about 13%), MAGE-ML - Microarray Gene Expression Mark-up Language (more than 11%), CellML - Cell Markup-Language (almost 10%), MAGE-TAB Microarray Gene Expression Tabular Format, MzML - Mass Spectrometry Mark-up Language and BED Format for NGS (all almost 8%), SED-ML - Simulation Experiment Mark-up Language (more than 6%), GFF – General feature Format (7%), SBRML - Systems Biology Results Mark-up Language (almost 4%).

SBML seems to play the key role for respondents for structuring and annotating data and models.

Q21 What formats do you use for structuring and annotating your data and models (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 82 Skipped: 45

Additionally, 24% scientists responded that they don't use any of the standard formats listed in the survey, and indicated other formats that they used instead that they felt were more appropriate for their own data - Self developed XML based, Matlab, kappa (rule-based format), PRIDE format, Modelica, GINML, PRIDE XML, matlab code without formal structure.

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014-2015

6. METADATA STANDARDS USED FOR STRUCTURING AND ANNOTATING DATA- - UPDATED

Q22 Which metadata standards do you use for structuring and annotating your data and models (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 78 Skipped: 49

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014-2015

MIAME - Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment is a metadata standard used by more than 34% respondents for structuring and annotating their data and models, perhaps reflecting a high level of transcriptomic data production by the respondents. Other metadata standards used by respondents include: MIRIAM - Minimal Information Required In the Annotation of biochemical Models (almost 18%), MIAPE - Minimum Information About a Proteomics Experiment (9%), MIASE - Minimum Information About a Simulation Experiment (8%) and MIARE - Minimum Information About a RNAi Experiment (more than 6%), ISA - Investigations Studies Assays (4%), MIMIx - Minimum Information about a Molecular Interaction Experiment (more than 2%), MINSEQE - Minimal Information about a high throughput SEQuencing Experiment (more than 2%). **More than 51% do not report using any metadata standards for structuring and annotating their data and models.** This is an important finding as it has implications for future data and model interoperability and can inform future plans for the ISBE data stewardship infrastructure. It is clear that this area should continue to be analysed in more detail in the near future.

7. ONTOLOGIES/VOCABULARIES USED FOR STRUCTURING AND ANNOTATING DATA-- UPDATED

More than 59% of respondents use **GO - Gene Ontology** for structuring and annotating their data. SBO - Systems Biology Ontology is used by more than 18%, BioPax - Biological Pathways Ontology (almost 13%), MGED - Microarray and Gene Expression Data Ontology (almost 13%). More than 6% use PSI-MS - Mass Spectrometry Ontology and more than 6% use PSI-MI - Protein Interaction Ontology. CHEBI - Chemical Entities of Biological Interest is used by more than 6% as well. PSI_MOD - Protein Modification Ontology is used by more than 5%; as is 5% of respondents use MESH - Medical Subject Headings, whereas more than 3% use PATO - Phenotypic Quality Ontology. **More than 28% do not use any vocabularies/ontologies for structuring and annotating their data and models.**

Q23 Which ontologies/vocabularies do you use for structuring and annotating your data and models (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 81 Skipped: 46

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014-2015

Out of the 81 respondents, 3 reported using additional categories: Plant Ontology (PO), XEO and Mapman.

IV. CURRENT DEMANDS FOR ISBE INFRASTRUCTURE WITH RESPECT TO STORAGE AND HARDWARE

It is clear from many of the pointers in the above sections, that future access to sufficiently high capacity computing but perhaps more importantly computing co-located with or with easy fast access to key datasets and managed secure data storage is of key importance for systems biology. These facilities will need also to provide data-centric services as extensively reviewed under the ISBE infrastructure reports for data and models management and data stewardship. As a reflection of the fundamental role of IT services in today's research and in compliance with the conclusions of the e-IRG White Paper (2013) ISBE infrastructure should supply integrated IT services (storage and hardware, and the middleware/software stack required to use them, according to the different requirements of the various user research areas. It should supply high quality services, accessible to all researchers throughout Europe. Users and e-Infrastructure service providers should work together in order to create and improve such type of tools. We should however

acknowledge that other aspects of computational infrastructure play a crucial role in making these services available such as computing networking and aspects of trust and security service provision.

The ISBE infrastructure is a complex network of physical and virtual resources designed to support a model-centric and data-centric approach to Life Sciences. The distributed, interconnected infrastructure envisaged by ISBE depends on the adoption of best practices, standards, technical infrastructure, and capacity for the management and distribution of data and models, and the management and sustainability of data and model management software.

However, researchers are increasingly interested in integrated services focused on their own problems, and much less in who delivers these services. Ultimately, researchers and infrastructure users tend to look for user-friendly and consistent access to all infrastructure services they might need, which should be simple to use and not costly to manage. With the scope of increasing importance of international research collaboration and the use of data, ISBE, along with other infrastructure providers, should reflect this need which is becoming ever more important.

As a living ecosystem, ISBE infrastructure must be flexible and able to change fast in accordance with the needs of users. ISBE should provide services which have demonstrable added value over commercial providers – in terms of services, facilities offered, scope and/or cost.

According to the e-IRG 2012 “Blue Paper” on Data Management the growing importance of data available everywhere and at every stage of research is causing a rapid increase in the amount of data available and the capacity needed for its storage.

Like the physical universe, the digital universe is large – by 2020 containing nearly as many digital bits as there are stars in the universe. It is **doubling in size every two years**, and by 2020 the digital universe – the data we create and copy annually – will reach 44 zettabytes, or 44 trillion gigabytes. (Turner)

For some areas, such as DNA sequencing, the estimated increase far exceeds this: the volume of public DNA sequence data doubles around every 9 months currently. This doubling time is substantially faster than current disk or CPU capacity-per-cost doubling times, of which Moore’s law is a projection.

(freely distributed for use by **NHGRI** <http://www.genome.gov/sequencingcosts/>)

As a reflection of the systems biology data infrastructure landscape, **Big Data management** and **Cloud computing** can be seen as areas of technological growth that may be explored for near-future exploitation as a means to fulfil some of ISBE’s future needs. We will outline some areas of immediate interest below:

To cope with **Big Data** - a collection of data sets so large and complex that it becomes difficult to process using on-hand database management tools or traditional data processing applications - new tools and methods are being developed, such as Hadoop and NoSQL data stores. Hadoop provides the necessary tools for several Big Data methods such as association rule learning, cluster analysis, pattern recognition, predictive modelling, and

others. NoSQL data stores allow for data to be partitioned across different machines, as there is no need to follow a fixed relational schema.

Cloud Computing - The “cloud” is not a separate computing infrastructure *per se* but a means of delivering, a range of services, which can be implemented on existing e-Infrastructures. Cloud computing is a broad term for systems that deliver hosted services over the Internet. The NIST definition of cloud computing is “a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction”.

Different types of services are broadly Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS where users are given access to a variable number of virtual servers and storage), Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS – where providers offer software development tools that are accessible via APIs and the consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure) and Software-as-a-Service (SaaS – where software applications are offered – e.g. as web services). Cloud instances can be private to a particular group or project, public - offered by a third-party provider over the internet (e.g. Amazon EC2), or hybrid.

Even though Cloud computing was the most highly cited area for IT spending in 2014 (Bio IT World Survey), it is not yet clear if the cloud is the best solution for all areas of scientific computing and storage of scientific data. Other infrastructure providers have already investigated provisioning cloud resources as pilots for making compute, limited storage, software, and in some cases datasets and reference data available as e-infrastructure. Notable examples include:

- The European Grid Infrastructure Federated Cloud (<http://go.egi.eu/cloud>), launched in 2014, which includes some life science applications, as well as tools for discovery, sharing and replication of a defined set of ELIXIR datasets
- The EBI and ELIXIR EMBASSY cloud pilot - The EBI Embassy Cloud is an service that provides secure, flexible infrastructure together with a range of open data and open source software to be used by bioinformaticians. (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/services>)

It will be important for the emergent ISBE infrastructure team to take on board the lessons already being learned from these pilot studies and as technology is moving forwards rapidly, this will need to be revisited in order to assess the optimal software stack, service model etc.

BioMedBridges (Building Data Bridges between biological and medical infrastructures in Europe), another ESFRI infrastructures project has recently produced a technology report on “current developments in the ICT e-infrastructure”. A workshop for BMS RI technical representatives with e-infrastructures (including ISBE) – “Preparing for the Data Deluge” held 15-16 May 2014, highlighted some of the current challenges in common across e-infrastructures. As one of the workshop outputs, delegates prepared a check-list of information (“Big Data Checklist for life sciences research infrastructures”) that needs to be

available in order to define the requirements of researchers for data-centric compute infrastructures, and which may serve to form the basis of dialogue between users and providers within ISBE. It is clear that users of the infrastructure need to be actively involved at all stages of infrastructure lifecycle, from requirements gathering, planning, implementation, active use and updating. At the same time, many potential users of compute infrastructure may not be sufficiently technically aware in this specialist area to comment fully, and so such a check-list will be used as a bridge.

It is important to acknowledge that ISBE is not alone in its need for e-infrastructure provision. A number of EU-wide projects (funded by a variety of funding calls including EU) are already in existence, offering, supporting and coordinating a wide range of services for compute, storage and data that may be drawn on by ISBE as it moves into its next phase. Indeed ISBE is already interacting with some of these projects via workshops such as the one outlined above, also a recent workshop “HPC in Health research” organised by DG CONNECT and DG Research and Innovation in Brussels 1-2 October 2014. Some of the major ones are outlined below.

TABLE - Existing key e-infrastructure providers across EU

Entity Name or Acronym	Area of expertise	URL reference
GEANT	Networking including coordination of design, implementation and management of interconnection domains between National Research and Education Network domains (1 per country). Provides physical hardware, services, software and middleware development for monitoring, also some single sign-on services.	www.geant.net
PRACE	Provision of very high performance computing resources (so-called tier 0 and also some tier 1 level). Access is granted via peer-reviewed project proposals, or to specific ‘calls’. Some software development, training courses and offers test access to some prototype systems.	http://www.prace-ri.eu
EGI – European Grid Infrastructure	Publically funded multi-site large-scale compute infrastructure, including multi-petabyte storage, with associated core services. Newer services include data-intensive research solutions including a new cloud-based offering (EGI federated cloud), and some life science-specific services including software and hosting of ELIXIR reference datasets.	http://www.egi.eu
RDA – The Research Data Alliance	An international collaboration for fostering cooperation and driving new solutions for data management and exchange thorough formation of working groups. Membership includes representation from non-EU	https://rd-alliance.org

	countries including US and Australia.	
EUDAT	Data infrastructure consortium that aims to build and provide a sustainable infrastructure including services for accessing, searching and preserving research data, including that stored in existing data repositories. Newer developments include the development of a federated open research data platform.	Http://www.eudat.eu

V. CONCLUSION

Systems biology looks at very large systems and deals with enormous amounts of complex and multi-modal data. To facilitate this, the data needs to be managed, stored and preserved in a cost-efficient way, with appropriate quality and safety assurances. It will also be necessary to provide secure access to the data across borders and domain boundaries. ISBE will need to tackle these complex issues on different levels. ISBE computational infrastructure will not equate purely to a set of large compute clusters or storage hardware; rather it will seek to plug the critical gaps between existing areas of provision, with an emphasis on data stewardship, software, data and expertise, while providing critical resources to underpin the work of the ISBE hub and nodes.

1. Data storage – computational projects in system biology produce huge amount of data, one project can produce several terabytes of the data that need to be stored for the long term. Development should focus at the possibility to extend the current storage capacities and also to develop the completely new technologies of data storage.

2. Data transfer – due to the complexity of projects in systems biology, many data sets from the same project may be produced in different places. For the analysis of the data, many different research groups in different places have to share the data. The fast way of the sharing and transferring the large amount of data is needed. For some projects this process can currently occupy up to 10% of the project time. Improved methods of data compression may also assist with data transfer.

3. Data processing – The analysis of the enormous amounts of data requires huge processing power and can take the majority of the project time. Improvements in the current CPU and GPU technologies as well as development of the new computational technologies will need to be monitored for leveraging within key parts of the infrastructure. Continuing development of the newer computer architectures and more effective algorithms are expected to improve the current situation.

4. Data generation – Data for many projects in system biology are generated during simulations. To improve this stage, not only improvement of the processing power is needed, but we also need to improve fast local storage of large temporary datasets.

5. Support for commercially sensitive and personally sensitive data. As stated in the data stewardship vision in WP 2, ISBE will support life sciences research, health research and commercial collaborations in these areas. ISBE infrastructure will need to have appropriate security protocols to handle a mixture of open and commercially sensitive data/models and open and commercial services.

ISBE computational infrastructure SHOULD:

- Actively Investigate interfacing with established and emergent e-infrastructure providers to assess how to best make use of existing resources and initiatives, and better define the gaps that need to be filled by ISBE-specific infrastructure..
- Ensure that there is sufficient high speed network connectivity between all constituent nodes to support appropriate data transfer at all stages in the data lifecycle.
- Work with existing e-infrastructure providers such as EGI, EUDAT, PRACE to define, offer and support a suitable software/middleware stack for secure data transfer between sites.
- Offer access to high-performance computing (supercomputing) and high-throughput computing (including grid computing) to underpin the major computational requirements of the ISBE community.
- Work with ISBE users, including data generators, and staff from data stewardship nodes and modelling nodes, to define, maintain and support a suitable user environment, including key open source software, data management and curation tools.
- Provide secure, managed long-term storage for key systems biology datasets, databases and commons infrastructure.
- Develop a clearly defined access policy and sustainable business model.

COULD:

- Provide a co-ordinated systems biology user community to pilot use of existing e-infrastructures such as EGI; also for seeding special interest groups in the Research Data Alliance to further technology watch in this area.

WILL NOT:

- Offer long-term unlimited storage for raw data. Since ISBE no longer uses the concept of specific 'Data production' nodes, raw data will generally remain the responsibility of the generating Institution,
- Seek to duplicate roles and services already offered by other ongoing organs such as Elixir; but will instead provide a coordinated infrastructure to support the specific requirements of systems biologists.

- Be prescriptive at this stage about the best computational platforms to underpin future ISBE service provision. (e.g. percentage of cloud-based offerings, specific virtual machine (VM) architectures)
- Provide open unlimited access to compute resources without accountability, defined by the ISBE Business Model.

VI. THE NEXT STEPS

Technology Watch will need to continue through the next stages of ISBE, in order to study technology updates in the computational and storage area and make recommendations on optimal implementation strategies as the project moves forwards and overall requirements become more clear. In particular

- (i) to investigate further and identify possible storage platforms, including cloud-based solutions*
- (ii) to identify and outline possible schemes for limited integration with commercial hardware and storage providers*
- (iii) to enable access to existing data*
- (iv) to investigate innovative developments in data-specific compression which could be applicable for use in ISBE infrastructure*
- (v) to analyse big data management with respect to ISBE needs*
- (vi) to further analyse ongoing and emergent data, Long-term storage, back up of data, Standards and curation requirements and possible solutions*

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Report on "E-Infrastructure support for the life sciences– Preparing for the data deluge" A BioMedBridges knowledge exchange workshop hosted by ELIXIR, 15-16 May 2014, Hinxton, UK https://zenodo.org/record/13942/files/WORKSHOP_REPORT_e-infrastructure_support_for_the_life_sciences.pdf